

INVESTIGATING THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL LITERACY AND METACOGNITIVE STRATEGIES IN ENHANCING THE COMMUNICATION SKILLS AMONG BSED-ENGLISH STUDENTS

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Investigating the Impact of Social Literacy and Metacognitive Strategies in Enhancing the Communication Skills among BSED-English Students

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to determine the impact of social literacy and metacognitive strategies to the communication skills of BSED-English students in a local college in Davao del Norte. The study is quantitative research that utilizes a descriptive-correlational approach and regression analysis. A sample of 214 randomly selected BSED-English students who were identified using stratified random sampling answered the surveys on the three variables. Furthermore, the statistical tool was used in computation of the data as well as the testing of the hypothesis at alpha 0.05 level of significance. The mean that was used to determine the levels of social literacy, metacognitive strategies, and communication skills, the pearson r that was used to determine the significant relationship between the social literacy, metacognitive strategies and communication skills, and the regression that was used to determine the significant influence of social literacy and metacognitive strategies on the communication skills of the respondents. Additionally, results showed that the level of social literacy, metacognitive strategies, and communication skills were all high in level. Results also revealed that there is a significant relationship between social literacy and communication skills. Likewise, there is also a significant relationship between metacognitive strategies and communication skills of the students. Moreover, results show that domains of social literacy such as intellectual skills, cooperation skills and social attitude and values can significantly influence communication skills. Finally, it was revealed that domains of metacognitive strategies such as planning and evaluation, mental translation, and problem solving can significantly predict communication skills of the respondents. Results imply that the variables are significant in improving the communication skills of BSED-English students.

Keywords: *social literacy, metacognitive strategies, communication skills, BSED-English students, Philippines*

Introduction

Communication skills hold immense significance among students, as they are the foundation for academic achievement and personal growth. Effective communication allows students to articulate their ideas, collaborate with peers, and participate actively in learning environments. However, a persistent problem is the widespread deficiency in communication skills, which can hinder students' progress. Insufficient proficiency in communication not only obstructs academic success but also impedes the development of vital social and professional competencies. It is imperative for educational institutions to address this challenge by providing resources and opportunities for students to improve their communication skills, as it is a critical life skill with far-reaching implications for their future success (Dababneh, 2019).

In India, it is known that the lack of communication skills is quite critical in students' coursework. The research findings indicate that a significant factor contributing to a lack of communication skills in India is a lack of formal education and training in effective communication methods. Additionally, this issue stems from a multifaceted landscape where language diversity is a focus on rote learning, and limited emphasis on interactive and practical communication within the education system all contribute to the challenge. While English is a widely used medium for higher education, many students struggle with fluency and effective articulation, hindering their ability to express their thoughts and ideas coherently. Thus, problem of communication skills in India needs attention and comprehensive solutions to improve educational and professional outcomes. Addressing this issue is crucial to ensuring that students and professionals are equipped with the necessary tools to succeed in an increasingly globalized world (Santosh, 2018).

In the Philippines, particularly in Batangas, studies indicated that teacher education students who have chosen English as their field of specialization often face significant communication skills challenges, specifically the fear of public speaking or communicating in front of an audience. Despite their academic focus on the English language, these students frequently encounter anxiety and apprehension when it comes to delivering presentations or engaging in public discourse. This fear can greatly impact their ability to communicate knowledge effectively and connect with their future students in the classroom. And to address these challenges, it's important to assess and evaluate how individuals perceive their own communication skills, as self-awareness plays a crucial role in improvement (Akkakoson, 2019).

Considering these factors, it is important to conduct a study that focuses on the emergences of communication skills within the learners specifically among BSED-English students considering the social literacy, and metacognitive strategies. This study is urgent to conduct because it was a concerning common phenomenon that can affect the learners' educational performance. If neglected it leads to reduction of self-esteem, and students had continued to struggle or experience the lack of communication skills, which can potentially affect their overall learning performances and professional opportunities. Moreover, it was socially relevant as it could leads to a better understanding of the relationship between social literacy and metacognitive strategies, paving way for important information that

offered strategies and perspectives regarding communication skills among students, particularly in the locality where the study was conducted.

There were several studies that had been conducted in related research endeavors such as the study by Tran Tin Nghi (2021) entitled, “A Study on Communication Skills Breakdowns between Native and Non-native Speakers in English Speaking Classes” revealed that many Vietnamese learners encountered challenges in English-speaking classes because of language differences, cultural variations, psychological barriers, limited vocabulary, and unfamiliar idiomatic expressions which led to communication barriers. Moreover, the study conducted by Mayerová (2018) entitled “The Effect of Language Preparation on Communication Skills and Growth of Students’ self-confidence” closely exploring the language preparation as well as their overall self-confidence. However, there is no further investigation into the factors that contribute to the level of communication skills from the influence of social literacy and metacognitive strategies to the students. To address this gap, the researcher sees the need to conduct a study that determines the impact of social literacy as well as metacognitive strategies on communication skills of the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) major in English students particularly in the local college of Kapalong, Davao del Norte.

Finally, the findings will be disseminated through publishing the study in the reputable academic journals focused on communication skills and student well-being. Also, the results of this study will be presented at local and regional educational conferences to share insights and gather feedback from peers. Consequently, by combining publication in a peer-reviewed journal with presentations at academic conferences, the researcher aimed to reach a broad audience of educators and researchers, helping to address the problems discussed and implement the suggested recommendations.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study is to determine the significant relationship between communication skills on the impact of social literacy and metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. To be specific, this study sought to answers the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of social literacy of BSED-English students in terms of:
 - 1.1. intellectual skills;
 - 1.2. social skills;
 - 1.3. cooperation skills; and
 - 1.4. social attitude and values.
2. To determine the level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students in terms of:
 - 2.1. planning and evaluation;
 - 2.2. person knowledge;
 - 2.3. directed attention;
 - 2.4. mental translation; and
 - 2.5. problem solving.
3. To determine the level of communication skills of BSED-English students in terms of:
 - 3.1. competence;
 - 3.2. discouragement;
 - 3.3. competence;
 - 3.4. body language; and
 - 3.5. dignification
4. To determine the relationship between;
 - 4.1. social literacy and communication skills; and
 - 4.2. metacognitive strategies and communication skills.
5. To determine the significant influence of the domains of social literacy and metacognitive strategies that can possibly predict communication skills.

Methodology

Research Design

This study was quantitative, as it quantified the problem by generating numerical data or data that could be transformed into usable statistics. Quantitative research is defined as a method for testing objective ideas by exploring the relationship between variables. These variables can be measured using instruments, and the resulting numerical data can be analyzed using statistical methods and structured methodologies such as surveys. Statistical data is typically collected in the form of numerical data and analyzed to draw conclusions that inform the final course of action (Apuke, 2017).

In the context of this study, the quantitative approach was chosen to systematically investigate and measure the impact of social literacy and metacognitive strategies on the communication skills of the respondents. Through, generating numerical data, the research aimed to provide a clear and objective understanding of how these factors influence effective communication. The use of quantitative methods

allowed the researchers to collect data that could be statistically analyzed, revealing precise insights and patterns that might not be evident through qualitative methods alone. Instruments such as surveys were employed to gather this numerical data, ensuring a structured and replicable approach to data collection.

Additionally, the researcher utilized a descriptive quantitative research design, specifically utilizing a descriptive-correlational research technique. The focus of descriptive-correlational research method is on describing relationships among variables without aiming to establish a causal link. This approach identifies patterns and associations between variables, using statistical methods to analyze data. While providing valuable insights, this method cannot prove causality, as there may be unaccounted variables or factors at play (Quaranta, 2017).

In the context of the study, the quantitative research design utilized a descriptive-correlational analysis to investigate the impact of social literacy and metacognitive strategies on communication skills. This research encompassed three key variables: social literacy and metacognitive strategies as independent variables, and communication skills as the dependent variable. The respondents of the study is consists of selected BSED-English students enrolled in the institution.

Respondents

This study involves the BSED-English students enroll in Academic Year 2023-2024 at Kapalong, College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology (KCAST) of Barangay Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. The respondents in the study were primarily drawn from this institution using the random sampling method. The respondents of the study were 214 samples out of the population of 457 BSED-English students during the first semester of A.Y. 2022-2023. The respondents were based on these pre-conclusion criteria: must be 18 years and above; male or female; and, who are first, second, third and fourth year BSED-English students of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. The students who are selected as respondents were chosen because of the focus of the study is on the impact of social literacy, metacognitive strategies into the communication skills of the students.

The researcher utilized the stratified sampling method to select participants of the study. This approach involves dividing a larger population into smaller groups that is based on specific characteristics relevant to the study. Rather than randomly selecting from the entire population, samples are chosen from each of these categories. This method improves sample representativeness by ensuring proportional representation of each subgroup, leading to more accurate and generalizable results. The choice of stratified random sampling aims to address the research goals and minimize potential bias in participant selection (Hayes, 2023).

In this study, stratified random sampling was employed to ensure that respondents from each year level of BSED-English students were proportionally represented, allowing for a more accurate depiction of the entire population. Data on the total population of students was first obtained from the Office Registrar by submitting a formal letter of request, and once gathered, this information was sent to a statistician. The statistician then calculated the appropriate sample size, ensuring that students from each year level were included in the sample according to their proportion within the overall population, thus enhancing the representativeness and reliability of the findings.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

Respondents	Population	Percentage	Sample
First Year	223	22.85%	104
Second-Year	136	13.94%	64
Third-Year	69	7.07%	32
Fourth-Year	29	2.97%	14
TOTAL	457	46.83%	214

The table displays information regarding the distribution of respondents among various academic years within the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English (BSED) students' population. It reveals that there are a total of 457 students, with 22.85% in their first year, 13.94% in their second year, 7.07% in their third year, and 2.97% in their fourth year. The sample size for this dataset is 214, consisting of 104 first-year students, 64 second-year students, 32 third-year students, and 14 fourth-year students.

Instrument

The researcher utilized adapted questionnaires from the web sources to measure the intended variables. These adapted questionnaires that were used in the study was undergo thorough the expert validation before the dissemination of the research questionnaires to the respondents. The researcher was utilizing instruments for Social Literacy based on the study of Az-Zahra et al., (2018) which consisted of 4 indicators such as intellectual skills, social skills, cooperation skills and social attitude and values with 20 statement items. The result of this instrument reveals that the ability of students' social literacy as follows: intellectual skill 34.1%, social skills 12.6%, cooperation skills 14.7%, and social attitudes and values 38.5%. Higher percentage indicates students' social literacy in their daily journal. While, the second set of questionnaires was based on Seo (2022) This has 5-point Likert scale type focusing on metacognitive strategies used by the learners based on the following indicators: planning and evaluation, person knowledge, directed attention, mental

translation and problem solving with 21 statement items. The result of this instrument reveals that person knowledge as the top subscale of strategy both students used. The third and last set of questionnaires is the dependent variable of the study communication skills, is based on the study of Akkuzu and Akkaya (2014) which consisted of 4 indicators such as competence, discouragement, body language, and dignification with 36 statement items. According to the results of this instrument, competence, discouragement, body language and dignification were found to be important dimensions of efficient communication for today's student teachers.

Likert scale, a five-point measurement tool, enables individual to convey their degree of agreement or disagreement with a specific statement. Typically, it offers five response options, allowing respondents to express the strength of their agreement or feelings towards the statement (McLeod, 2023). In this study, the 5-point Likert scale was utilized to assess the levels of respondents' social literacy, metacognitive strategies, and communication skills.

The scale was employed to assess agreement or disagreement with statements regarding the influence of social literacy and metacognitive strategies on communication skills among learners. This scale facilitated data collection that could be analyzed to determine the impact of these factors on communication skills. Respondents utilized the scale by selecting a numerical response, ranging from 'always' to 'rarely,' corresponding to their agreement level with each statement. Scores across items were then totaled to provide participants with an overall score. Additionally, the questionnaire's overall effectiveness was evaluated through consolidation of feedback and assessments from expert validators, ensuring its reliability and suitability for the study.

Procedure

The following steps were done to collect the data for this study.

Questionnaire Formulation and Development. The researcher searched the questionnaires from reputable journal articles and related internet research which can be positively related to the three variables.

Revision and Validation of Questionnaires. The document was then submitted to the panel of experts for evaluation and contextualization. Upon receiving feedbacks and corrections, the researcher followed the advice of those revision experts until it was approved for administration.

Seeking the Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher first made a permission letter addressed to the Vice President of the Academic Affairs (VPAA) of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology which was signed by the researcher herself and noted by her research adviser and the director for research and development. Then, after the permission was approved by the VPAA, the researcher has explained and informed the BSED-English students who are the respondents of the procedure of conducting the study after securing their approval from the given written consent.

Distribution of Questionnaires. Survey questionnaires in printed forms were distributed individually to the respondents with the help of the resource students of this study.

Collection and Tabulation of Data. At this point, the research instruments will be collected after the students completely answering it, and will be gather together to tabulate the data gathered. From the final data, conclusions will be drawn and recommendations will be presented based on the results obtain.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in computation of the data as well as the testing of the hypothesis at alpha 0.05 level of significance.

Mean. This was used to determine the levels of social literacy, metacognitive strategies and communication skills.

Pearson r. This statistical tool was used to determine the significant relationship between the social literacy, metacognitive strategies and communication skills.

Regression. This was used to determine the significant influence of social literacy and metacognitive strategies on the communication skills of the respondents.

Ethical Considerations

To guarantee the appropriate execution of this research and the well-being of all individuals participating in this study, I adhered rigorously to the highest ethical considerations. These considerations ensured the participants' safety, rights and trust in the researcher, and the purpose of the study were given appropriate action and justice. These ethical considerations are the following: informed consent, risk of harm, anonymity and confidentiality, and conflict of interest (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Informed Consent. The respondents are fully aware of the nature of the study, the intended use of their data, and any potential consequences. To participate, they need to give informed permission, acknowledging their right to access their data and the option to withdraw at any time. The informed consent process serves, to some extent, as a legal agreement between the researcher and participants (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In the context of this study, respondents were provided with an informed consent form before their participation. They were first oriented about the study's purpose, benefits, risks, and funding, enabling them to make an informed decision on whether to participate or decline.

Risk of Harm, Anonymity and Confidentiality. It ensures that respondents' personal information, such as names and identifying details, remains confidential throughout the study, safeguarding participants against potential harm or adverse outcomes. Anonymity also helps prevent biases, as researchers are not influenced by participants' personal characteristics. Maintaining participant anonymity often involves using codes or pseudonyms instead of actual names and implementing measures to secure the confidentiality of any collected personal information (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In this study, in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, other steps were taken to safeguard the privacy and security of the collected data. Personal information, such as names and addresses, was carefully taken out to ensure that the data remained anonymous and clean. The researcher securely maintained all data throughout the study and, in accordance with regulations, will responsibly destroy it three years after the study's conclusion. This approach reflects a strong commitment to upholding confidentiality and ethical standards in data management and storing data.

Given the potential risks of publishing sensitive information, particularly in causing social harm, the data was kept confidential to mitigate such risks. To address concerns about privacy, survey questions were designed to exclude personal details like names, emails, or contact numbers, ensuring the protection of respondents' identities.

Conflict of Interest. It pertains to instances where personal considerations, such as financial interests, could potentially compromise an investigator's professional judgment in conducting or reporting research. Conflicts of interest in research, whether stemming from existing relationships or prior actions, should be transparently disclosed during the ethical approval process. This allows the committee to provide guidance on managing these conflicts, ensuring that personal interests or commitments do not compromise the study's integrity. Conflicts may involve financial or nonfinancial benefits and can impact a researcher's impartiality, undermining confidence in results (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In the context of this study, the researcher and respondents shared the role of students, which effectively mitigated any potential conflict of interest. However, conflicts could arise if the researcher had the power to coerce participation through pressure or authority, such as threats, benefit termination, or punishment. For example, a student-researcher within the same institution might inadvertently create a conflict by using their influence to pressure peers into participating, potentially offering rewards or threatening social repercussions for non-compliance. Therefore, it was essential for the researcher to actively avoid any conflicts of interest, including financial incentives, to uphold the integrity of the study and ensure ethical standards were maintained throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

Level of Social Literacy in Terms of Intellectual Skills

Table 2. *Level of Social Literacy of Students in Terms of Intellectual Skills*

Intellectual Skills	Mean	Description
· Having the ability to identify and define issues and problems	4.01	High
· Making hypothesis and writing conclusions based on information	3.87	High
· Possessing the ability to analyze and synthesize information through intellectual capabilities	3.83	High
· Distinguishing between statements based on whether they convey factual information or subjective opinions	3.87	High
· Using the previous learning experience to shape the capacity to communicate complex ideas clearly and persuasively	4.08	High
OVERALL	3.83 3.83	High

The level of social literacy of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, intellectual skills. The responses of BSED- English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 2 is the level of social literacy of BSED-English students in terms of intellectual skills. The data revealed that the level of social literacy in terms of intellectual skills had a total mean of 3.93 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of social literacy of BSED-English students in terms of intellectual skills is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 5 – Using the previous learning experience to shape the capacity to communicate complex ideas clearly and

persuasively, geared the highest mean score of 4.08 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 3 – Possessing the ability to analyze and synthesize information through intellectual capabilities, got the lowest mean score of 3.83 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Level of Social Literacy Terms of Social Skills

The level of social literacy of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, social skills. The responses of BSED- English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 3 is the level of social literacy of BSED-English students in terms of social skills. The data revealed that the level of social literacy in terms of social skills had a total mean of 4.12 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of social literacy of BSED-English students in terms of social skills is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 1 – Living in harmony and work with others together and similarity respect their rights, geared the highest mean score of 4.20 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 3 – Learning to control the self in times of chaos and difficulties, got the lowest mean score of 4.04 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 3. *Level of Social Literacy of Students in Terms of Social Skills*

Social Skills	Mean	Description
Living in harmony and work with others together and similarly respect their rights	4.20	High
Having social sensitivity and awareness when talking with other people	4.16	High
Learning to control the self in times of chaos and difficulties	4.04	High
Exchanging thoughts, ideas and experience with others	4.13	High
Aiming to cultivates social relationships with others both within and beyond the school environment	4.13	High
OVERALL	4.07	High

Level of Social Literacy in Terms of Cooperation Skills

The level of social literacy of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, cooperation skills. The responses of BSED-English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 4. *Level of Social Literacy of Students in Terms of Cooperation Skills*

Cooperation Skills	Mean	Description
Taking an active role in different group activities in school	4.01	High
Participating in a group discussion inside and outside classroom	3.93	High
Working with others in accomplishing desired and established academic goals	3.98	High
Implying willingness to foster collaborative efforts within diverse group activities	3.95	High
Being actively embrace diverse perspectives in group assignment to foster inclusivity and diversity of thoughts	3.99	High
OVERALL	3.97	High

Presented in Table 4 is the level of social literacy of BSED-English students in terms of cooperation skills. The data revealed that the level of social literacy in terms of cooperation skills had a total mean of 3.97 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of social literacy of BSED-English students in terms of cooperation skills is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 1 – Taking an active role in different group activities in school, geared the highest mean score of 4.01 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 2 – Participating in a group discussion inside and outside classroom, got the lowest mean score of 3.93 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Level of Social Literacy in Terms of Attitude and Values

The level of social literacy of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, social attitude and values. The responses of BSED- English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 5 is the level of social literacy of BSED-English students in terms of social attitude and values. The data revealed that the level of social literacy in terms of social attitude and values had a total mean of 4.24 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of social literacy of BSED- English students in terms of social attitude and values is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 3 – Knowing how to respect each of the right of every student within the school premises, geared the highest mean score of 4.36 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 2 – Making decision that involves emulation of positive attitude and values, got the lowest mean score among the survey of 4.19 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 5. *Level of Social Literacy of Students in Terms of Social Attitude and Values*

Social Attitude and Values	Mean	Description
· Knowing the general values and protocols were established the needed inside the school premises	4.24	High
· Making decision that involves emulation of positive attitude and values	4.19	High
· Knowing how to respect each of the right of every student within the school premises	4.36	High
· Developing sense of belongingness and responsibility with others	4.22	High
· Developing sense of brotherhood and sisterhood among students and peers	4.20	High
OVERALL	4.24	High

Summary of the Level of Social Literacy

Presented in Table 6 is the overall level of social literacy of BSED-English students in terms of intellectual skills, social skills, cooperation skills, and social attitude and values. The data revealed that the level of social literacy of BSED-English students has a total mean of 4.07 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that social literacy is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents.

Table 6. *Level of Social Literacy*

Indicators	Mean	Description
Intellectual Skills	3.93	High
Social Skills	4.12	High
Cooperation Skills	3.97	High
Social Attitude and Values	4.24	High
OVERALL	4.07	High

Further, the highest mean is 4.24 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of social literacy in terms of social attitude and values is oftentimes manifested.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is intellectual skills which obtained a mean of 3.93 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of social literacy in terms of intellectual skills is oftentimes manifested.

Additionally, social skills obtained a mean of 4.12 which means high. This indicates that the level of social literacy in terms of social skills is oftentimes manifested.

Lastly, cooperation skills obtained a mean of 3.97 which means high. This indicates that the level of social literacy in terms of cooperation skills is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Metacognitive Strategies in Terms of Planning and Evaluation

The level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator planning and evaluation. The responses of BSED-English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 7 is the level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students in terms of planning and evaluation. The data revealed that the level of metacognitive strategies in terms of planning and evaluation had a total mean of 4.09 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students in terms of planning and evaluation is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 1 – Having a plan in the head for how should going to speak either inside and outside the class, geared the highest mean score of 4.19 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 2 – Having a goal and plan in the head as started to speak in front of the class, got the lowest mean score of 4.02 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 7. *Level of Metacognitive Strategies of Students in Terms of Planning and Evaluation*

Planning and Evaluation	Mean	Description
· Having a plan in the head for how should going to speak either inside and outside the class	4.19	High
· Having a goal and plan in the head as started to speak in front of the class	4.02	High
· Thinking of similar text that may have to speak to, before speaking	4.07	High
· Thinking back to how to speaks, and about what might do differently next time.	4.08	High
· Having a goal and plan of what going to speak towards others	4.11	High
OVERALL		

Level of Metacognitive Strategies in Terms of Person Knowledge

The level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator person knowledge. The responses of BSED-English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 8. *Level of Metacognitive Strategies of Students in Terms of Person Knowledge*

Person Knowledge	Mean	Description
Being aware of the information being conveyed and feel confident to speak without experiencing nervousness	3.78	High
Finding that writing in English is more difficult than reading, listening and speaking in English	3.60	High
Feeling that speaking comprehension in English is a challenge	3.99	High
Using the prior knowledge as a basis for creating meaningful learning goals and plans to improve the English learning	4.07	High
Utilizing various strategies to enhance the proficiency in expressing ideas in English	4.03	High
OVERALL		

Presented in Table 8 is the level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students in terms of person knowledge. The data revealed that the level of metacognitive strategies in terms of person knowledge had a total mean of 3.90 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students in terms of person knowledge is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 4 – Using the prior knowledge as a basis for creating meaningful learning goals and plans to improve the English learning, geared the highest mean score of 4.07 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 2 – Finding that writing in English is more difficult than reading, listening and speaking in English, got the lowest mean score of 3.60 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Levels of Metacognitive Strategies in Terms of Directed Attention

The level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator directed attention. The responses of BSED-English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 9 is the level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students in terms of directed attention. The data revealed that the level of metacognitive strategies in terms of directed attention had a total mean of 3.86 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students in terms of directed attention is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 1 – Trying to get back on track when losing concentration in communication, geared the highest mean score of 4.07 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 3 – Having no difficulty of understanding what wanted to speak during communication, got the lowest mean score of 3.50 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 9. *Level of Metacognitive Strategies of Students in Terms of Directed Attention*

Directed Attention	Mean	Description
Trying to get back on track when losing concentration in communication	4.07	High
Focusing harder on the words when having trouble in communicating	4.02	High
Having no difficulty of understanding what wanted to speak during communication	3.50	High
Recovering the concentration right away, when the mind wonders what to speak	3.76	High
Recognizing actively the strength and weakness that hindering to focus on any specific aspects of communication	3.94	High
OVERALL	3.86	High

Levels of Metacognitive Strategies in Terms of Mental Translation

The level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator mental translation. The responses of BSED-English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 10 is the level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students in terms of mental translation. The data revealed that the level of metacognitive strategies in terms of mental translation had a total mean of 3.81 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students in terms of mental translation is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 2 – Translating the previous knowledge about words and grammars during the communication process, geared the highest mean score of 3.90 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 4 – Grasping easily and creatively interpret ideas or concepts, got the lowest mean score of 3.69 which indicates

a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 10. *Level of Metacognitive Strategies of Students in Terms of Mental Translation*

Mental Translation	Mean	Description
Translating keywords as to speak inside and outside of the class	3.85	High
Translating the previous knowledge about words and grammars during the communication process	3.90	High
Translating word by word as going to speak	3.81	High
Grasping easily and creatively interpret ideas or concepts	3.76	High
Employing strategies to translate challenging words and comprehend them better	3.69	High
OVERALL	3.85	High

Level of Metacognitive Strategies in Terms of Problem Solving

The level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator problem solving. The responses of BSED-English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 11 is the level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students in terms of problem solving. The data revealed that the level of metacognitive strategies in terms of problem solving had a total mean of 4.09 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of metacognitive strategies of BSED- English students in terms of problem solving is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 1 – Using the experience and knowledge to help understand the words during the communication, geared the highest mean score of 4.26 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 5 – Monitoring quickly the way I speak, to adjust the interpretation if realizing that the words are incorrect, got the lowest mean score of 3.94 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 11. *Level of Metacognitive Strategies of Students in Terms of Problem Solving*

Problem Solving	Mean	Description
Using the experience and knowledge to help understand the words during the communication	4.26	Very High
Using the general idea of the text to help guessing the meaning of the words that is hard to speak	4.08	High
Using the words that I understand to guess the meaning of the words that is hard to understand	4.08	High
Thinking back to everything else that I speak, to see if there are words that needs corrections and improvements	4.09	High
Monitoring quickly the way I speak, to adjust the interpretation if realizing that the words are incorrect	3.94	High
OVERALL		

Summary of the Level of Metacognitive Strategies

Presented in Table 12 is the overall level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students in terms of planning and evaluation, person knowledge, directed attention, mental translation, and problem solving. The data revealed that the level of metacognitive strategies of BSED-English students has a total mean of 3.95 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that metacognitive strategies is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents.

Further, the highest mean is 4.09 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of metacognitive strategies in terms of planning and evaluation and also problem solving is oftentimes manifested.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is mental translation which obtained a mean of 3.81 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of metacognitive strategies in terms of mental translation is oftentimes manifested.

Additionally, person knowledge obtained a mean of 3.90 which means high. This indicates that the level of metacognitive strategies in terms of person knowledge is oftentimes manifested.

Table 12. *Level of Metacognitive Strategies*

Indicators	Mean	Description
Planning and Evaluation	4.09	High
Person Knowledge	3.90	High
Directed Attention	3.86	High
Mental Translation	3.81	High
Problem Solving	4.09	High
OVERALL	3.95	High

Lastly, directed attention obtained a mean of 3.86 which means high. This indicates that the level of metacognitive strategies in terms of directed attention is oftentimes manifested

Level of Communication Skills in Terms of Competence

The level of communication skills of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator competence. The responses of BSED-English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 13 is the level of communication skills of BSED-English students in terms of competence. The data revealed that the level of communication skills in terms of competence had a total mean of 3.69 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of communication skills of BSED-English students in terms of competence is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 2 – Believing that I can understand what people say clearly and correctly to me during conversations, geared the highest mean score of 3.79 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 3 – Expressing the feelings and thoughts clearly in the class without any hesitation, got the lowest mean score of 3.60 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 13. *Level of Communication Skills of Students in Terms of Competence*

Competence	Mean	Description
Feeling confident when I make a presentation outside and inside the community	3.71	High
Believing that I can understand what people say clearly and correctly to me during conversations	3.79	High
Expressing my feelings and thoughts clearly in the class without any hesitation	3.60	High
Talking easily to my teachers as well as my friends during different conversations in the class	3.61	High
Paying attention to stress and intonation and demonstrate diverse strategies when speaking	3.77	High

Level of Communication Skills in Terms of Discouragement

The level of communication skills of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator discouragement. The responses of BSED-English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 14 is the level of communication skills of BSED-English students in terms of discouragement. The data revealed that the level of communication skills in terms of discouragement had a total mean of 3.83 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of communication skills of BSED-English students in terms of discouragement is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 4 – Worrying about choosing correct word but still managing to overcome this challenge, geared the highest mean

score of 3.91 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 3 – Using unnecessary words while talking however I am actively working on improvement, got the lowest mean score of 3.73 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 14. *Level of Communication Skills of Students in Terms of Discouragement*

Discouragement	Mean	Description
Cannot behaving naturally during speech but still managing to overcome this challenge	3.78	High
Finding it challenging to articulate the thoughts and feelings effectively, but still trying the best to express myself	3.85	High
Using unnecessary words while talking however I am actively working on improvement	3.73	High
Worrying about choosing correct word but still managing to overcome this challenge	3.91	High
Being afraid of encountering negative thoughts and to be ridiculed by people, yet still managing to overcome this challenge		
OVERALL	3.90	High

Level of Communication Skills in Terms of Body Language

The level of communication skills of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator body language. The responses of BSED-English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 15 is the level of communication skills of BSED-English students in terms of body language. The data revealed that the level of communication skills in terms of body language had a total mean of 3.84 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of communication skills of BSED-English students in terms of body language is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 3 – Showing my approval during a conversation actively by nodding, geared the highest mean score of 4.16 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 2– Keeping the eye contact and maintaining good posture while speaking to someone, got the lowest mean score of 3.94 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 15. *Level of Communication Skills of Students in Terms of Body Language*

Body Language	Mean	Description
Using facial expressions and hand gestures while speaking and communicating to someone	4.12	High
Keeping the eye contact and maintaining good posture while speaking to someone	3.94	High
Showing my approval during a conversation actively by nodding	4.16	High
Using body language to convey ideas more convincingly during speech	4.02	High
Wanting that listeners show that they listen to me while I am speaking inside and outside the community	4.12	High
OVERALL	3.84	High

Level of Communication Skills in Terms of Dignification

The level of communication skills of BSED-English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator dignification. The responses of BSED-English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 16 is the level of communication skills of BSED-English students in terms of dignification. The data revealed that the level of communication skills in terms of dignification had a total mean of 4.01 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated

that the level of communication skills of BSED-English students in terms of dignification is oftentimes manifested.

Further, item no. 3 – Wanting people to respect and recognize my ideas while speaking, geared the highest mean score of 4.19 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

In contrast, item no. 1 – Preferring monologues rather than dialogues in a certain communication, got the lowest mean score of 3.71 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Table 16. *Level of Communication Skills of Students in Terms of Dignification*

Dignification	Mean	Description
Preferring monologues rather than dialogues in a certain communication	3.71	High
Being open to criticisms and any different viewpoints while speaking to help improve the communication	4.08	High
Wanting people to respect and recognize my ideas while speaking	4.19	High
Being a good listener to perceive what is said accurately and completely	3.99	High
Understanding the situation, she/he is in she/he is speaking	4.07	High
OVERALL	4.01	High

Summary of the Level of Communication Skills

Presented in Table 17 is the overall level of communication skills of BSED-English students in terms of competence, discouragement, body language, and dignification. The data revealed that the level of communication skills of BSED-English students has a total mean score of 3.84 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that communication skills is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents.

Further, the highest mean is 4.01 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of communication skills in terms of dignification is oftentimes manifested.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is mental translation which obtained a mean of 3.69 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of communication skills in terms of competence is oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Additionally, discouragement obtained a mean of 3.83 which means high. This indicates that the level of communication skills in terms of discouragement is oftentimes manifested.

Table 17. *Level of Communication Skills*

Indicators	Mean	Description
Competence	3.69	High
Discouragement	3.83	High
Body Language	3.84	High
Dignification	4.01	High
OVERALL	3.84	High

Lastly, body language obtained a mean of 3.84 which means high. This indicates that the level of communication skills in terms of body language is oftentimes manifested.

Significant Relationship Between Social Literacy and Communication Skills

Presented in Table 18 is the result of the significant relationship between social literacy and communication skills, $r(114) = .578$, $p < .001$. Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a positive and significant relationship between social literacy and communication skills.

Thus, this means that there is a significant relationship between social literacy and communication skills. This further explains the two variables simultaneously increases or decreases together, without giving any data on which one of the variables causes the increase or decrease of either variable.

Table 18. Significant Relationship Between Social Literacy and Communication Skills

Variables Correlated	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Social Literacy	4.07	.578	<.001	H₀ Rejected
Communication Skills	3.90			

Significant Relationship Between Metacognitive Strategies and Communication Skills

Presented in Table 19 is the result of the significant relationship between metacognitive strategies and communication skills, $r(114) = .713, p < .001$. Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a positive and significant relationship between metacognitive strategies and communication skills.

Table 19. Significant Relationship Between Metacognitive Strategies and Communication Skills

Variables Correlated	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Metacognitive Strategies	3.95			
Communication Skills	3.90	.713	<.001	H₀ Rejected

Thus, this means that there is a significant relationship between metacognitive strategies and communication skills. This further explains the two variables simultaneously increases or decreases together, without giving any data on which one of the variables causes the increase or decrease of either variable.

Significant Influence Between Social Literacy and Communication Skills

Presented in Table 20 is the significant influence of the domains or indicators of social literacy towards the level of communication skills among BSED-English students. The results showed that three domains of social literacy, intellectual skills, cooperation skills, social attitude and values, appear to be statistically significant predictors of the level of communication skills of BSED-English students – intellectual skills ($\beta = 0.193, p = .004$) cooperation skills ($\beta = 0.201, p < .001$) and social attitude and values ($\beta = 0.164, p = .022$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected.

The beta value, $\beta = 0.193$, indicates that for every unit increase of intellectual skills, the level of communication skills among BSED-English students will also increase by 0.193 units. Likewise, the beta value of $\beta = 0.201$, indicates that for every unit increase of cooperation skills, the level of communication skills among the BSED-

Table 20. Significant Influence Between Social Literacy and Communication Skills

Independent Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	P-value	Decision @=0.05
	B	SE	Beta			
(Constant)						
Intellectual Skills	0.193	0.066	0.216	2.91	.004	H₀ Rejected
Social Skills	0.062	0.065	0.075	0.95	.342	H₀ Accepted
Cooperation Skills	0.201	0.062	0.245	3.249	.001	H₀ Rejected
Social Attitude And Values	0.164	0.071	0.175	2.305	.022	H₀ Rejected
Dependent Variable: Communication Skills						
Note: R = 0.585, R² = 0.342, F-ratio = 27.183, P-value = < .001						

English students will also increase by 0.201 units. Further, the beta value of $\beta = 0.164$, indicates that for every unit increase of social attitude and values, the level of communication

skills among BSED-English students will also increase by 0.164 units. Therefore, intellectual skills, cooperation skills and social attitude and values are the only indicators of social literacy that can significantly influence the communication skills of BSED-English students.

On the other hand, the other one domain – social skills ($\beta = 0.062, p = .342$) – do not have a significant influence on communication skills. At 0.05 level of significance, the p-values of the one domain exceeded 0.05. This suggests that the one domain was not a

significant predictor of communication skills.

Moreover, communication skills explained a significant proportion of variance in students' communication skills, the $R^2 = 0.342$, $F = 27.183$, $p < .001$. The $R^2 = 0.342$ shows that the model predicts 34.2 % of the statistical variation observed in the level of communication skills among the respondents. The coefficient of alienation which is 65.8 points to the extent at which other indicators or domains not included in the study may explain the variance observed in the level of communication skills among BSED-English students.

Significant Influence Between Metacognitive Strategies and Communication Skills

Presented in Table 21 is the significant influence of the domains or indicators of metacognitive strategies towards the level of communication skills among BSED-English students. The results showed that three domains of metacognitive strategies, planning and evaluation, mental translation, problem solving, appear to be statistically significant predictors of the level of communication skills of BSED-English students – planning and evaluation ($\beta = 0.12$, $p = .013$) mental translation ($\beta = 0.133$, $p = .019$) and problem solving ($\beta = 0.35$, $p < .001$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected.

The beta value of $\beta = 0.12$ indicates that for every unit increase of planning and evaluation, the level of communication skills among BSED-English students will also increase by 0.12 units. Likewise, the beta value of $\beta = 0.133$ indicates that for every unit increase of mental translation, the level of communication skills among BSED-English students will also increase by 0.133 units. Further, the beta value of $\beta = 0.35$ indicates that for every unit increase of problem solving, the level of communication skills among BSED-English students will also increase by 0.35 units. Therefore, planning and evaluation, mental translation and problem solving are the only indicators of metacognitive strategies that can significantly influence the communication skills of BSED-English students.

Table 21. Significant Influence Between Metacognitive Strategies and Communication Skills

Independent Metacognitive Strategies	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	P- value	Decision @=0.05
	B	SE	Beta			
Person Knowledge	0.12	0.048	0.154	2.51 1	.013	H ₀ Rejected
Directed Attention	0.071	0.053	0.083	1.33 5	.18 3	H ₀ Accepted
Mental Translation	0.054	0.063	0.063	0.85 4	.394	H ₀ Accepted
Problem Solving	0.133	0.056	0.172	2.36 9	.019	H ₀ Rejected
	0.35	0.048	0.43	7.241	< .001	H ₀ Rejected

Dependent Variable: Communication Skills
 Note: R = 0.743, R₂ = 0.552, F-ratio = 51.282 P-value = < .001

On the other hand, the other two domains, person knowledge ($\beta = 0.071$, $p = .183$) and directed attention ($\beta = 0.054$, $p = .394$) do not have a significant influence on communication skills. At 0.05 level of significance, the p-values of the two domains exceeded 0.05. This suggests that the two domains were not a significant predictor of communication skills.

Moreover, communication skills explained a significant proportion of variance predicts 55.2 % of the statistical variation observed in the level of communication skills among the respondents. The coefficient of alienation which is 44.8 points to the extent at which other indicators or domains not included in the study may explain the variance observed in the level of communication skills among BSED-English students.

Conclusions

Drawing upon the results, conclusions were formulated in response to the questions posed in the preceding chapter. The respondents consistently reported a significant prevalence of social literacy, indicating that this variable is oftentimes observed by students.

Based on the result of social literacy as perceived by students, it was determined to be high. This means that the students often observe the presence of the variable. Moreover, based on the result of the metacognitive strategies of the students, it can be also drawn that the level of metacognitive strategies among BSED-English students was high. This means that the students often manifest the variable. In Addition, the students were assessed the preparedness level for communication skills, and it was determined as high. This means that the communication skills of the BSED-English students are oftentimes manifested.

Furthermore, the correlation between the social literacy and communication skills revealed a significant relationship between the two variables. The study shows that social literacy has a moderate, positive, and significant relationship with the communication skills among BSED-English students. This means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

In addition, the correlation between the metacognitive strategies and communication skills also revealed a significant relationship

between the two variables. The study also shows that metacognitive strategies has a moderate, positive, and significant relationship with the communication skills among BSED-English students. This means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

Based on the result of regression analysis, in social literacy three domains have shown significant influence to the communication skills. This means that the domains – intellectual skills – cooperation skills and social attitude and values– are significant predictors of communication skills of BSED-English students. Consequently, the model explains a significant portion of the variance in the communication skills of the respondents, while the remaining refers to other variables that have not been included in the study that may also affect the communication skills of the respondents.

Lastly, the regression analysis of metacognitive strategies has three domains that significantly influence the communication skills of the respondents. This means that the domains – planning and evaluation, mental translation and problem solving – are significant predictors of communication skills. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Consequently, the model explains a significant portion of the variance in the communication skills of the respondents, while the remaining refers to other variables that have not been included in the study that may also affect the communication skills of the respondents.

Based on the previously mentioned findings from the study, the following recommendations were formulated. Among the social literacy indicators, it was found that intellectual skills has the lowest mean. Therefore, the following recommendations are given.

It is hereby recommended that educational institutions focus on enhancing the quality and comprehensiveness of students' intellectual skills, particularly in terms of critical thinking and communication. To achieve this, institutions should prioritize the incorporation of interactive and collaborative learning experiences, promote a supportive and inclusive learning environment, and provide opportunities for students to develop their problem-solving abilities and creativity. By prioritizing these intellectual skills aspect of social literacy, educational institutions can better prepare students for success in an ever-evolving and interconnected world.

Based on the results, mental translation has been identified as having the lowest mean among the metacognitive strategies indicators. Consequently, a set of targeted recommendations was formulated to improve and strengthen this specific aspect. Several targeted recommendations were proposed to address and enhance this aspect.

Therefore, it is hereby recommended that educational institutions incorporate targeted interventions aimed at enhancing students' mental translation abilities. This could involve providing explicit instruction on effective mental translation techniques, offering opportunities for practice and feedback, and fostering a supportive learning environment that encourages students to reflect on their own thinking processes. Additionally, by prioritizing the development of mental translation skills, educational institutions can empower students to become more effective and confident communicators.

The findings also revealed that competence resulted in the lowest mean among communication skills indicators. The findings emphasize the need for improvement in the competence of the students. Therefore, the following recommendations are given.

It is hereby recommended that the educational institutions and instructors may focus on fostering competence among students. This can be achieved through the implementation of comprehensive strategies aimed at enhancing students' competence in various aspects of communication skills, including confidence in presentations, expressing feelings, understanding and translating words, as well as active listening and comprehension during speaking. Educational institutions and instructors can play a crucial role in fostering these skills by providing opportunities for practice, offering constructive feedback, and creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment. Furthermore, by prioritizing the development of these communication skills, students can become more effective and confident communicators, capable of expressing themselves with clarity and understanding others with empathy.

Moreover, for the benefit of future researchers, a recommendation is made to consider employing a mixed-method approach when delving into the intricate interplay between social literacy, metacognitive strategies, and communication skills. Although the present study centered on a quantitative research design involving 214 students, the utilization of a mixed-method approach holds promise for multiple reasons. The integration of quantitative data derived from surveys with qualitative insights obtained through interviews or focus groups stands to furnish a comprehensive panorama of students' perspectives and dispositions.

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